

SYSTEMS THINKING AUGMENT AESTHETICOLOGY APOTHEOSIS

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ABSTRACT

The aestheticology firms are a vital part of the global economy and are challenged to become efficacious to stay competitive. Most of them have not yet adopted to bolster the ability to think holistically to apply the unique strength of *systems thinking* concepts to overcome competition, attain efficiency, improve value co-creation process, and aestheticology paragon. This represents a compelling research gap. Hence, the aim of this study is to investigate the influences of *systems thinking* in the design and development of aestheticology products from the view point of fashion. The author has introduced KLAS (Kanban, Lean, Agile, Scrum) methodologies, and multiple case studies that focus on delivering the best possible evidence-based research and perspective on aesthetics design integrated with emerging technologies. The contribution of this research provides the essential principles of aestheticology to attain socio-economic and ecological benefits. Finding reveals that aestheticology designers ought to use the *systems thinking* with emerging technology innovation as “holistic and interdisciplinary” approach for the transformation of value chain to overcome competition to attain aesthetics transcendence and stakeholder satisfaction. This study provides precept to aestheticology enterprises, smart fashion wearable designers, non-government organizations (NGOs), academia, entrepreneurs, industry practitioners, investors, and policymakers to assuage economic benefit and ecological development for the contemporary society. Future researchers can build on systems thinking to examine the limitations of this model by using empirical researches.

Keywords

Systems Thinking, KLAS Methodologies, Innovation, Aesthetics, Technology, Fashion

INTRODUCTION

The role of knowledge creators is consistently growing. New knowledge and ideas are great value to the business. Innovation is considered as new creations of knowledge significance and critical to economic growth. The literature provides substantial evidence regarding the value of innovation and technological change that are the most important sources of progress in productivity growth. Such progress has pivoted to a systems perspective and has the potential to enhance innovation outcomes for businesses, and industries. The systems approach improves the learner’s understanding of a system, its variables, its outcomes, and the relationships among the system’s components. Systems thinking is big picture thinking and the key principles of systems thinking as applied to leadership and management discipline that concerns the understanding of a system by investigating the interactions between the components of that system.

Aesthetics is defined (i) pertaining to a sense and love of beauty, (ii) concerned with emotion and sensation as opposed to intellectuality, (iii) an idea of what is aesthetically valid. Aesthetics is also a study of new way of seeing and of perceiving the world as well as the mind to interpret something as being beautiful. Aesthetic cognition is no longer the sole orbit of philosophy and art. Nowadays, the application of aesthetics covers well beyond the study of fashion, sensory discrimination, culture, taste, values, instincts, emotions, experience, judgement and nature. Fashion is often applied to wearable within a time context and is vital with regards to aesthetics. The term "aesthetics" is construed to mean the study of arts and perception of an object based on what one sees, feel, hear, smell and even taste. Aesthetics integrated with technology, - “Aestheticology” a term coined by the author, is the integration of aesthetics and technology designed to appeal to any sense to create "significant form" perceiving beauty, perfection and emotion and demonstrate understanding of shape, form, color, texture, symmetry, and proportion in product design and development.

When one think about aestheticology management to attain design aesthetics epitome, one must approach it as a systems thinker. The first is to look for parts of the problem that characterizes as a system. Meaning where are the inputs, outputs, throughput, boundaries, feedback and control mechanisms, interactions with other systems? To build systems kinetics models that capture a system, one should explore how cycles and delays affect the overall behavior of the system. Also, one always looks out for emergent properties that arise as a result of interactions across a system. As shown in figure 1, the author has shown systems thinking approach with a novel orientation to integration of aesthetics and technology design complexity to simplicity to attain aestheticology paragon.

Fig.1 Systems thinking approach to aestheticology management

STUDY JUSTIFICATION

The aestheticology business is a vital part of the global economy and challenged to achieve efficacy to stay competitive. During challenging times, it's paramount to understand the long-term consequences of decisions and how to be more strategic about developing organization strength. Most aestheticology firm's management have not adopted to unique strength of *systems thinking*, and organizational learning to bolster the ability to think holistically to overcome competition. This represents a compelling research gap and a knowledge vacuum in the literature, therefore it is worth investigating the systems thinking to empower aestheticology epitome from the view point of fashion.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of *systems thinking* that includes KLAS (Kanban, Lean, Agile, Scrum) methodologies in the design and development of aestheticology from the view point of fashion.

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Kanban is a scheduling system of visual management aimed at just-in-time delivery. Many companies have tried Kanban scheduling and implementing Kanban without a clear idea of the goal is doomed to fail. Hence, most of them go back to conventional approach applying enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems. Kanban is about taking all ambiguity out of the information flow throughout the supply chain eliminating the individual judgments and is a great tool for revealing the real leverage points for improvement in delivery systems.

Lean movement was born in manufacturing industry (automotive industry) aiming at loss reduction and sustainable production. Later, adapted for software development with relevant lean principles. A lean company follows a learn – measure – build cycle, conducts many tests, continuously connects with customers to understand, and improve the value creation process. Lean methodology helps launch software products far more

quickly and cheaper than conventional methods. So far, the lean methodology hasn't spread quickly through most industries. Many have tried, only few achieved successes. Very few companies are lean yet, because most still have trouble understanding the fundamental link between information and production. Based on extensive experience of the author, the "Systems Thinking" contributes significantly by providing an overall framework to lean methodology. Lean systems thinking is a methodology aims at creating unique lean enterprise that sustains growth by aligning customer satisfaction and organizing human activities to deliver higher productivity to the society.

Agile was born to improve productivity in software development and expanded into other disciplines such as Marketing. When a team follows the relevant value principles that can be considered 'agile', then time-focused, iterative philosophy allows to build a product incrementally. One of its primary benefits is the ability to adapt and change at any step to supply relevant products to the market. Among information communication technology professionals, agile methodology is the primary approach.

Scrum is a software development methodology for managing knowledge work and addresses complex adaptive problems while creatively delivering products with highest value creation. Scrum assumes that the systems development process is an unpredictable, complicated process, enhancement of the commonly used iterative object-oriented development cycle, and workable techniques that a development team build systems.

Both (**Scrum and Kanban**) methodologies follow the principles of Agile and Lean. They track processes via scheduling system to ensure transparency. Scrum limits them by time units — iterations, Kanban limits work in progress per workflow state. All the above-mentioned methodologies are linked with each other and integral parts of Systems Thinking", as shown in figure 2.

To understand how systems thinking in aestheticology management works, the author has introduced a novel holistic - interdisciplinary approach for enhancing organizational performance through KLAS (Kanban, Lean, Agile, Scrum) methodologies, a term coined by the author. Software development methodology is a framework that is used to structure, plan, and control the process of developing an information system. Although systems thinking and KLAS methodologies operate at two different levels, the author has learned from personal experience that an understanding of system thinking dramatically improves the learning curve of KLAS techniques and practices.

Over the past two decades KLAS (Kanban, Lean, Agile, Scrum) methodologies have been steadily gaining popularity in various business fields. Although many companies are currently executing or leaning towards these methodologies, only a few understand the entire process to capture value for project management. Lack of knowledge among the staff of an organization leads to lower motivation and poor performance.

Hence methodology basics must be learned and shared by every employee involved. Considering the above, the following are the reasons the author has chosen "systems thinking" in this study:

- (i) Being lean is essential to adapt and survive the cut throat competition.
- (ii) Due to rapid growth of technology market, particularly software sector introduces other industries to adopt lean and scrum mindsets.
- (iii) Trend toward perfection makes everyone proud designing and developing products to offer the best price and best quality.
- (iv) Proper management reduces stress, increases welfare and satisfaction.

<https://realtimeboard.com/blog/choose-between-agile-lean-scrum-kanban/>

Fig. 2 “Systems Thinking” composed of KLAS Methodologies

A SYSTEMS PERSPECTIVE

Complex systems can't be individual parts. One need a broader perspective to see the big picture. Complex systems can't be individual parts. One need a broader perspective to see the big picture. The systems thinking enable to visualize a complex system as a framework with the interrelationships between internal and external elements that influence the system. Completion of a systems diagram allows better understanding how it works, the delays in the system how to improve the system based on the concluded data.

Systems thinking has evolved as an alternative to the old paradigms. Many methodologies are derived from the systems thinking. With systems thinking, designers learn how their organization interact. Systems Thinking was originally proposed as an analytical paradigm to different scientific disciplines like biology, psychology, the social sciences, etc. Nowadays systems thinking has become an established perspective on the management process. One goal of systems thinking in management is conceptual understanding of the structure and behavior of complex organizations and the benefits of systems thinking can be explained using Brooks' Law [1]. As shown in figure 3, a common systems perspective on design and development process consists of three subsystems, namely sensors/controller system, software development system, and customer System.

Software development environment requires often change during the design and development life-cycle to meet business needs, minimizing headaches for development teams. The software development system has requirements and resources as inputs, and software as output. The inputs and outputs are flow of information. Ex: the customer system has software (e.g. information about the software's actual functionality) as one input, and it produces requirements (e.g. information about the software's desired functionality) as one output. The outputs of such a system are not only dependent on the inputs, but they also depend on the system's state. This create dynamics that result in time delays between input changes and corresponding output changes of a system. Delays can cause two effects: (i)the system needs more time to respond to changes, (ii) delayed flows of information result in outdated information. Both undesirable effects of delays can be explained referring to Brooks' Law and Figure 3.

Fig.3 A systems perspective of software development

In this study, the author has identified two sources of delays in software development processes, that are generally addressed by agile methods. The first source of delays is the separation of process definition and process execution, that is a frequent practice in software development management. Contrary to this, agile software development methods propose an integrative approach toward process definition and process execution. The second source of delays are buffering strategies, that are widely used in software development management.

Based on authors extensive experience, there are many ways, randomly one could explore better configurations in a software development project. Injecting randomness, as shown in the above figure 3, into a software development project, the objective is not to create chaos, but to create new avenues for the information to flow within the project team and a novel way to derive the outcome. Using such practices increase project's chances for success. The chance of success increases for the project by exploring new organizations and structures through a process of small (safe-to-fail) changes that can lead to unplanned, but ultimately superior performance.

AEASTHETICOLOGY: DISRUPTION IN FASHION INDUSTRY

This paper contributes to the discussion on systems thinking research to develop the concept of aesthetics disruption through technology highlighting its connection to the fashion design. Aesthetics disruption in the context of fashion, and technology, the author identifies four core components driving aesthetic disruption contributing to transforming actors' mental models: (i) engagement of the senses - fundamental to aesthetic disruption is the sensual, embodied experience of actors, (ii) experience of dissensus - by engaging with heterogeneous artefacts confronting with established frameworks of perception , (iii) exposed assumptions - designer practices can support actors in understanding and re-shaping system behaviors , (iv) reflexive actors - the relationship between actors' experience and their detachment from existing mental models requires reflexivity. Thus, aesthetics knowledge can contribute to the integration of technology and fashion design to achieve aestheticology transformation.

AESTHETICOLOGY SYSTEMS OVERVIEW

Consumers expect usability by default and are seeking wearables experience pleasure to stimulate senses to evoke positive emotion. Aesthetically pleasing designs bestow positive attitude in the users and is paramount to meet the above needs. Smartness in wearables is generating pragmatic systems that integrates aesthetics and interaction design with advanced technologies that impacts on reshaping human lives and behaviors, as shown in figure 4.

Fig.4 Aestheticology Systems Overview

Even though evidence suggest that aesthetics matters in almost every aspect of human thought and behavior, so far, aesthetics as a neglected dimension of research in the area of digital technologies. The rapid proliferation of digital technologies and the increasing application activities necessitate a rigorous attempt at understanding how technology, fashion design and aesthetics relate. The author emphasize that the purpose of this study is not to suggest the predominance of aesthetic considerations over others to advocate better balance of aesthetics design dimensions in digital technologies.

Computational aesthetics [2] a field of artificial intelligence deals with the computational assessment of beauty in domains of human creative expression. Aesthetic features are used in conjunction with specialized algorithms to provide numerical aesthetic assessments to correlate well with domain-competent or expert human assessment. Computational aesthetics can also improve understanding of human aesthetic perception.

The Halo Effect [3]- Aesthetics is the power of beauty in design and paramount with regards to user experience (UX) because it impacts the UX of a product in many ways. A phenomenon called “*the halo effect*” means humans tend to assume that good-looking people have other positive qualities aside from their looks. The same is true for product design. Good looking products and user interface are perceived as more valuable. “Beauty is in the eye of the beholder”. Aesthetics are in all our senses. Aesthetic design is a 4D experience. The virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies becomes important for digital designers to consider the 4D experience.

Blockchain has the potential to revolutionize how supply chains operate in most industries, including medical aesthetics and can provide transparency matching perfectly the nagging problems of the medical supply chain.

Sensors - Aesthetics in the context of human-computer interaction has been focused primarily on usability. Wearables have increased in user adoption in recent years. The fitness trackers on the market have distinct aesthetics and the relationship between activity tracker and wearer resulting aesthetic experience. The author presents themes which wearable designers should be conscious of during the design process: sensor qualities, properties of the sensors, the usage context, and other influencing factors.

AESTHETICOLOGY ACTUALIZE USER BOND & LOYALTY [4]

Fashion as a thriving industry and to meet a broad spectrum of consumer needs, the aesthetic aspects of fashion is a compelling area for research. It is important to stimulate more research on the aesthetic aspects of fashion design. To that end, the author is investigating the aesthetics of fashion design and digital technology. Aesthetics refers to sensory perception and sensuous knowledge. Aesthetic details are paramount to design for emotions. Aesthetics is the power of beauty, taste and style in design for one to feel in their senses and signifies making the first impression. This brings balance between the mercurial desires of customers and the needs of the society. Fashion designers look to various indicators and influences for new ideas of fashion, technology, and aesthetics.

Why one experience certain feelings as gratifying? The author argues, as per evolutionary psychology, that human beings aesthetically prefer materialistic features and patterns that are beneficial for the development of the senses for survival. The principles of aesthetic pleasure, in general, operating across the senses can be explained on the following basis: (i) paramount outcome for merest means, (ii) unity in assortment, (iii) most progressive, yet acceptable, and (iv) flawless match.

While some do not like digital technology's pervasiveness and impersonal influence, others want functionality and emotion driven aesthetics. Aesthetically pleasing designs concoct assuagement in the users and makes customers care more about the product and becomes loyal to the brand. When one perceives beauty with sense of deeper pleasure. Excitement happens from the start with the aesthetic design and makes the customers form a nexus that goes beyond the initial feeling. Aesthetic design also makes the first feeling long lasting and formulate the manacle with the customer. In general, customers are looking for more aesthetic value and are increasingly open to exploring creative possibilities to meet their needs. Considering the above, the author has coined and introduces the 5C (comfort, care, convenience, context of usability, communication) experiences that are at the epi-center of aestheticology value creation for the smart fashion wearables, as shown in the figure 5:

Fig 5. Five C experience at the Epi-Center of Aestheticology Value Creation

- (i) Comfort - aesthetic contentment is the art of entwining level of ease effortlessly to create value.
- (ii) Care - Aesthetic care is the combination of art, fashion, technology in a manner to offer reliability and safety in smart fashion wearables that rejuvenate health and wellness.
- (iii) Convenience - In crafting customer experiences, the perception of convenience is as vital as the actual benefits of saved time and effort. Wearables offer convenience that connects to a smartphone using Bluetooth to provide alert to the user receives a call, SMS, and email. A lighting control system offers versatility, particularly the element of convenience with regards to light control (on and off) and to illuminate pathways throughout the fashion show.

- (iv) Context of usability - Usability is minimalistic design. Aesthetics in the context of usability is concerned with the relationship between aesthetics, and ergonomics. It is directly correlated with usability because it affects the emotional state of users, which in return can affect users' interaction with the smart fashion wearable.
- (v) Communication – Personal sense of reality is built upon understanding of communication. The art of human communication is profoundly important in an everchanging technological society. Wearable devices can replace smartphone and tablet to provide important message communication via aesthetic forms of expression that can influence cultural and social development. Marketing is a conversation. Keeping customers engaged is a daunting endeavor. Creating a strong presence in the market requires innovative ways to communicate with new & existing customers.

Branding is a marketing term to build and maintain brand identity. Brand loyalty is a customer behavior stencil where users repeat purchases over time. Fashion brands use ingenious marketing strategies to build brand loyalty. The following are the few tips to maintain brand loyalty: (i) provide value, (ii) keep quality high, (iii) engage with customers continually, (iv) solicit feedback from customers, (v) give the customers a reason to come back, and (vi) unceasingly innovation to stay relevant.

AESTHETICOLOGY DESIGN CLASSIFICATIONS

In this study, the author describes why one experience certain feelings as gratifying to senses and aesthetics experience is restricted to the (dis)pleasure that is derived from sensory perception. The literature provides evidence in evolutionary psychology thinking that human beings aesthetically prefer environmental patterns and features that are beneficial for the development of the senses' functioning. Nowadays, customer's expectations have evolved to experience pleasure (usability) to stimulate senses and evoke emotion much more than functionality. Hence aesthetics design is paramount to satisfy the usability needs. The following are the four key classifications with their elements aestheticology designs, as shown in figure 6:

Fig.6 Aestheticology Design Classification

- (i) **Visual** - the light that reflects from the beautiful design acts as a magnet for eyes and includes the elements such as *color, shape, pattern, line, texture, visual weight, balance, scale, proximity, and movement* to attain visual aesthetics.
- (ii) **Sound** - ears perceive a whole another level of aesthetics design enabling the power of sound aesthetics that includes the elements such as *loudness, pitch, beat, repetition, melody, pattern, and noise*.
- (iii) **Touch** - skin is the largest organ in human body helping to experience the material aesthetics involving the elements such as *texture, shape, weight, comfort, temperature, vibration, and sharpness*.
- (iv) **Taste and Smell** are the senses that helps experiencing aesthetics even more deeply involving the

elements such as *strength, sweetness, sourness and texture (for taste)*.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the research methodology includes:

1. Exhaustive literature review.
2. Multiple case study on the aestheticology companies to provide analysis to obtain a perspective on the aestheticology products such as smart watches, smart ring and smart bra.

Literature review is composed of four segments mentioned below:

Segment 1: The literature on using KLAS methodologies in distributed development software projects has steadily been growing. However, to date, there is little effort made to systematically select, review, and synthesize the literature on this topic. The author has conducted an exhaustive literature review of the primary studies that report using KLAS (Kanban, Lean, Agile, Scrum) methodologies.

This study explores various terms broadly and the search keywords include explanation on the following sections mentioned above, as shown in figure 1, 2 & 3: (a) introduction, (b) research background that includes KLAS (Kanban, Lean, Agile, Scrum) methodologies, and systems thinking perspective on software development for aestheticology products.

Segment 2: The literature review also focuses on the following principal constituents (mentioned above, as shown in figure 4, 5 & 6) that are co-related to each other to drive aestheticology enterprises to be successful : (i) aestheticology and the disruption in the fashion wearable industry (ii) aestheticology systems overview understanding how digital technologies relate to aesthetics from the view point of fashion, (iii) aestheticology actualize user bond and loyalty through the five C experience and value creation, (iv) aestheticology design classification with their elements creating emotions as gratifying to senses and aesthetics experience derived from sensory perception.

Segment 3: The author introduces the systems thinking and modeling methodology as a conceptual and analytical method relevant to the design and development of aestheticology products from the view point of fashion. This approach is based on the system dynamics methodology developed for the theory of information feedback systems to understand the decision-making process and for the development of stimulating mathematical models in computing. The development of systems thinking, and modeling methodology involves the following five distinct phases and can be used separately or individually, for value added purpose as shown in figure 7:

- (i) Problem structuring involves scope and boundaries consisting of (a) problem areas concerning to stakeholders, (b) collection of information and data, (c) conducting group sessions for creative problem structuring.
- (ii) Causal loop modeling – conceptual models of the problem is created through (a) key variables identification, (b) behavior for the key variables, (c) developing influence among the key variables, (d) discussing dynamics of the behavior, (e) identification of system archetypes, (f) identification of leverage points, (vii) developing strategies to intervene.
- (iii) Dynamic modeling involves the following phases: (a) development of a high-level systems map of a potential simulation model, (b) defining variable types, (c) collecting detailed and relevant information and data, (d) construction of a computer simulation model, (v) producing graphical and output of the model, (e) verifying model equations and validate the model's behavior, (f) performing sensitivity tests, (g) test and design policies/procedures with the model to address management concerns, (h) developing test strategies.

- (iv) Scenario planning and modeling includes strategies and policies for all stakeholders: (a) developing general scope, and timeframe, (b) identification of key drivers that could have a significant impact on the decisions, (c) constructing pro/con scenarios, (d) simulating the scenarios with the model, (e) evaluation of the performance of the strategies with the model for each scenario.
- (v) Implementation and organizational learning, most beneficial and enduring outcomes of systems thinking and modeling, includes (a) preparing a report for all the stakeholders, (b) communicate outcomes and insights to all stakeholders, (c) developing a detail picture for the simulation model, (iv) develop and use the learning lab process to facilitate learning for stakeholders.

Fig. 7 Systems thinking & modeling methodology

Segment 4: Innovation should be ‘holistic and interdisciplinary’ approach and an integral part of the systems thinking to encompass all the determinants of innovation. An innovation system is a system in which innovations emerge due to the unceasing interaction between all stakeholders to create value. The key drivers of innovation in contemporary innovation system discussed in the literature are: knowledge flow, institutions, economic competence and interactive learning, as shown in figure 8:

Fig.8 The Innovation Systems Approach comprised of six “I” concept

The author introduces six “I” concept (mentioned below) for the for the innovation process and recommends for the entrepreneurs and business leaders to execute to create value in an aestheticology venture or an existing enterprise.

1. Initiation - successful innovations are personal drive to innovate.
2. Imagine - imagination are the results of insights and focus on building ideas.
3. Improve - innovative ideas are a great step, but enhancing them is as important, if not more.
4. Inquire - test for product viability unceasingly and engage with prospective customers continually.
5. Influence - it’s vital to gather the support needed to continue working on the project to show a compelling opportunity.
6. Impregnate- continue to find data points through interactions with prospective customers to iterate about the testing so that continual learning and progress takes place.

Firms that compete based on technology innovation strategy need to contend with how their products, process and service delivers value. Enterprises need better *systems thinking* in their strategic delivery actions. The success of the firm depends on all stakeholders to interact to co-create value. Literature shows the application of systems thinking help to maximize the return on innovation investment that drives profitability, sustained growth, and competitive advantage. Technology leaders responsible for delivering technology solutions in complex systems markets also need to develop their employees to think in terms of systems, adopt systems practices, and apply relevant strategic tools to leverage systems thinking. Innovation systems are considered a key factor to enterprises’ long-term success. Considering the important role of innovation to the firm, an innovation systems model should be designed using systems thinking approach. The aim of the model is to enhance innovation activity in the firms of manufacturing industrial sectors. Systems thinking methodology has been used to uncover the complexity of the innovation systems framework and reveal the underling structures which generate change.

As shown in figure 9, the author introduces the “Perpetual Product, Process & Service Innovation (P^3SI)”, - a holistic-interdisciplinary approach that is synergetic with *systems thinking* to create unique product, process, service, management, and strategy for sustainable development of aestheticology products that truly works in practice. P^3SI , a term coined by the author, is essential to the development of new products, processes, services and innovative climate for the sustainable success factors of an enterprise to create value. Perpetual innovation ensures high quality of the products and services to maintain legal certainty through intellectual property protection that helps to establish as a major player in the market raising the profile and unique differentiation from the competitors to attain the sustainable competitive advantage Perpetual innovation creates superior and unique products and services. To create and sustain perpetual innovations, legal measures makes economic sense to attain perpetual creation to protect. [5].

Fig. 9 Systems Thinking and P^3SI Synergetic Approach

Multiple Case Study and Perspective

In the social science, multiple cases study involves in-depth investigation of the cases related to circumstantial conditions. The case study research had an outstanding position in many disciplines and industries ranging from fashion, technology, aesthetics, cognitive diversity, psychology, anthropology, sociology, and administrative science.

To meet the research objective, multiple case study methodology has been applied to analyze the process and impact of aestheticology paragon criteria, particularly in the context of aesthetics in fashion design. Information through extensive literature review, published reports, company website sources and various related databases has been used to explore regarding the three aestheticology brands mentioned above. The author emphasizes that value to be co-created, aestheticology firms should engage with all the stakeholders and community to ensure maximum stakeholder participation in value creation process. These engagements always foster stakeholder action and instill a sense of pride and confidence in them.

Based on the three case studies (Huami/Amazfit, OM Signal/OM Bra, & Ringly), this research demonstrates that the integration of aesthetics, and digital technologies from the point view of fashion can inexorably facilitate the value creation.

The fashion industry is mostly influenced by the impingement of socio-cultural -economic trends. This social trend may lead to a greater customer interest in the materials used, their origin and their processing methods, demanding more transparency and accountability on behalf of the aestheticology firms.

The aestheticology business has been subject to technological changes. The emergence of the Internet and improvements in wearable and digital technologies has accelerated the information flow of contemporary trends and brands from the customer to the retailer. Innovations like matrix coding, the co-creation of products and online shopping has made the decision and purchase of aestheticology products easier and more convenient for customers.

For many fashion brands, aesthetics is fundamental to brand strategy to provide added value to attract and meet consumers aesthetic needs to attain competitive advantage. Marketing aesthetics deals with dazzling consumers by their sensory experiences – tactile, visual, gustatory, and auditory. These sensory experiences create the first impression and the initial decision consumer make of aestheticology products. Smart fashion wearable brands, such as smart watches, combine the aesthetics with the functionality of smart watches. While the battle of wrist-worn devices is exponentially growing, companies are exploring the next wearable to make ‘smarter’ such as smart jewelry. Ventures, such as Ringly, have developed ring-based wearables with a variety of capabilities ranging from notifications to sleep tracking with aesthetics as an experience and awareness systems for emotional communication. The forms of tracking feature have been offered in smartphones and smart watches. In recent years the number activity trackers sold has significantly grown with aestheticology companies.

In this study the "aestheticology firm cases (Huami/Amazfit, OM Signal/OM Bra, & Ringly) " being studied from aestheticology brands perspective and their actions, existing in a specific time and place. Summary of the three aestheticology brands are outlined below and shown in figure 10:

Huami was founded in 2013 in China and the largest wearable device in the world with over 50 million units sold so far and achieved 17% global market share. The mission is to seamlessly connect biomechanical signals and daily activities with smart data services with to promote healthy living transforming the way individuals connect with the Internet. The company Huami is also the exclusive provider of wearable technology for Xiaomi and maker of the Mi brand (www.huami-usa.com/).

Fig.10 Aesthetics Products

The aesthetics product such as Amazfit PACE provides the features and benefits:

- Track speed, time, calories, pace, heart rate, cadence, elevation, and running distance
- Music (Without Smart Phone): connect to Bluetooth.
- GPS: track route and distance, water and dust resistance.
- Notifications: incoming calls, messages, emails and other apps.
- Full color touch display.
- Battery Life: Up to 5 days.
- Customize watch face by uploading personal photos.

Ringly was founded in 2013 in USA to make jewelry smart- fundamentally change the perception of jewelry as an aesthetics wearable (smart jewelry ring) that supports Apple iOS and Android Operating System software. Ringly operates with a passionate team working to create and build the aesthetics products that embraces creativity and innovation to create sustainable value —the intersection of fashion and technology with emphasis on aesthetics design with unique creation and design of aesthetic deliberation, and continuous innovation that creates value (<https://ringly.com>).

OMSignal was founded in 2011 in Montreal (Canada) with a vision to design, develop, manufacture and market sports bra that captures deep and accurate body signals. The smart bra is aesthetically designed on technology platform that sells to companies doing business in health, wellness, worker safety, and sports. The biometric smart wear platform allows any business to pair comfortable, everyday apparel that captures medical-grade biometric

data, with revolutionary AI algorithms and technology. As a result, businesses can change their approach to and within the health market. Our apparel picks up the body's signals using strategically placed ECG, respiration, and physical activity sensors (<https://www.omsignal.com/>).

CONTRIBUTIONS & FINDING

This research bestows the following valuable insight:

- (i) application of systems thinking and perpetual product, process, service innovation to frame the discussion on the inter-disciplinary domain of aesthetics, fashion design and digital technology.
- (ii) The four key classifications with their elements defined in aestheticology designs can act as a guide for design practitioners interested in employing aesthetic disruption to help realize their transformative aims in diverse social systems.
- (iii) provides precept to aestheticology enterprises, smart fashion wearable designers, non-government organizations (NGOs), academia, entrepreneurs, industry practitioners, investors, and policymakers to assuage socio-economic benefit for the contemporary society.

Finding reveals that aestheticology designers ought to use the *systems thinking* with emerging technology innovation as “holistic and interdisciplinary” approach for the transformation of value chain to overcome competition to attain aesthetics transcendence and stakeholder satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

In today’s business world, design thinking and systems thinking are still considered two separate universes. The author, as a practitioner for more than four decades, contends that integration of systems thinking with design thinking has augmented the chances of creating the right designs, particularly in aestheticology product design. The “design thinking” community can learn from the “systems thinking” community and vice versa.

Despite the advances in software development and management, the software projects continue to suffer schedule delays and budget overruns. The Brooks’ Law confirms that adding more manpower to a delayed software project makes it much worse in terms of delivery. Simply put, it is always costly to add people to a delayed project. When sequential constraint is significant, adding people late in a project will make it later.

The role of aesthetics is to bring the phenomenal experience of pleasure, beauty, and satisfaction to the expression, appreciation of ideas, objects, and processes. In this view raw emotions activate modes of thought that become mediated as feelings about the focal subject that help determine the level of pleasure, beauty, and satisfaction. The cross-modality principles of aesthetic pleasure and the rationale behind these principles is an evolutionary one. If certain patterns in the environment contribute to the functioning of human being senses, it is reinforcing to expose to the patterns. Hence, aesthetic pleasure is derived from seeing, hearing, touching, smelling/tasting, and thinking certain patterns that are beneficial to primary sense’s functioning.

The author argue that aesthetic disruption is the essence of competency in design, particularly in relation to the transformation of fashion. By placing the concept of aesthetic disruption in the context of social systems and contextualizing this through empirical illustrations in fashion industry has exciting potential systemic impact and broad applicability. By bringing focus on the important role in the process of aesthetic disruption in social systems, this research helps design practitioners to create more intentional and impactful interventions.

The benefits in learning from the three cases (Huami/Amazfit, OM Signal/OM Bra, & Ringly) are relevant today and in future, as many designers have a strong interest in the relationship of aesthetics and performance tempered by material properties, digital technologies and economics. The tangible relationship of aesthetics, material deposition, technology, fashion has been masterfully engaged in the aestheticology brands (mentioned above).

The realization of aestheticology has been enabled by several factors: (i) technology has been getting smaller and better in performance, (ii) fashion and technology companies want to expand their markets and looking for something new. From now on, things can only get better for aestheticology brands.

There is abundant evidence to suggest that aesthetics matters in almost every aspect of human thought and behavior. The research framework proposed in this study is far from being exhaustive. It is important to reiterate

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that the purpose of this research work is not to suggest the predominance of aesthetics considerations over other disciplines. Rather, it is to advocate better balance of major design dimensions in digital technologies, aesthetics and style, a balance that is much more needed for the aestheticology design apotheosis.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sterman, J.D. (1992). System dynamics modeling for project management. Unpublished manuscript, Cambridge, MA, web.mit.edu/jsterman/www/SDG/project.pdf.
- [2] Kang, Z; Harrel, S; Ji X. (2012). Computational Aesthetics: On the Complexity of Computer-Generated Paintings , <https://www.mitpressjournals.org/doi/abs/10.1162/LEON.a.00366>.
- [3] Cai, S; & Xu, Y, (2014). Designing Not Just for Pleasure: Effects of Web Site Aesthetics on Consumer Shopping Value, International Journal of Electronic Commerce , Volume 15, Issue 4 p.159-188 <https://doi.org/10.2753/JEC1086-4415150405>.
- [4] Padhi, P.K. (2018). Fashion Design, Digital Technology, Aesthetics, and Contemporary Society – A Critical Review, International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Biotechnology, Vol. 5, Issue-6, p. 9-20, DOI: doi.org/10.31033/ijrasb.5.6.2.
- [5] Padhi, P.K (2018). A Quest towards Fashion Design Protection Model for the Intellectual Property Rights Global Regime, International Journal for Research in Applied Sciences and Biotechnology, Vol. 5, Issue-5, p. 4-14, DOI: doi.org/10.31033/ijrasb.5.5.2

BIOGRAPHY

Prafulla Kumar Padhi, a serial entrepreneur, has over 42 years of global business experience and held the

Founder, CEO and Chairman of the Board positions for more than 25 years and managed up to US\$1.2 Billion revenue operations. His education qualification includes a Master of Science degree from the prestigious Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), Cambridge, USA and a graduate of the Ivy League Wharton School of Business, University of Pennsylvania (USA) and holds seven diploma certificates from the Ivy League Columbia University (USA), the Ivy League Dartmouth College (USA), and Kellogg School of Management (USA). For more than 40 years, as a pioneer, Mr. Padhi has been involved in entrepreneurial venture endeavors in disruptive technologies and smart fashion wearable ventures globally. So far, he has done business in 46

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